

THE VALUE OF COOPERATIVE EDUCATION FOR MIXED-AGE GROUPS

Sadullayeva Manzuna

Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry, Assistant

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10574293>

Annotation: This article explores the value of cooperative education within mixed-age groups, emphasizing its impact on academic performance, social and emotional development, and preparation for a diverse society. It delves into the principles of cooperative learning, benefits of mixed-age grouping, and strategies for successful implementation. The essay also addresses challenges and provides insights into curriculum design, assessment methods, and overcoming potential stereotypes. The goal is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the significance of cooperative education in mixed-age settings.

Key words: cooperative learning, learner-centered approach, teacher-centered approach, multi-age grouping, socio-emotional development, informal learning groups, formal learning groups, cooperative base groups, cognitive and meta-cognitive skills, communicative language coaching

Introduction:

In the realm of education, the approach to learning has witnessed significant transformations over the years. One such approach that has gained recognition for its effectiveness is cooperative education, particularly when implemented within mixed-age groups. This essay delves into the multifaceted value of cooperative education, exploring how it fosters a dynamic learning environment, promotes social and emotional development, and prepares individuals for the complexities of a diverse society.

Teaching foreign languages in academic establishments brings out some responsibilities and effective advantages to the academic system of our country wherever each chance is accessible for all ages. The high demand for learning English is taken into thought and each facilities area unit supplied with the assistance of recent technologies and strategies. Moreover, the perception from that analysis was mentioned with benefits of exploitation cooperative learning strategies in rising potency of learning foreign languages. The cooperative learning strategy promotes students' active learning by making simulated real-life language atmosphere. With the implementation of cooperative learning within the foreign instruction, students' area supplied with loads of opportunities to participate, experience, move and join forces in foreign

acquisition within the cooperative cluster, students work along, interacting face to face with the identical goal of learning, also as aiding one another (Borich, 2007).

One of the most important functions of the paper is to come back up with the thought for effectively coping with approaches of teaching English to totally different aged students and to recommend exploitation numerous strategies in numerous categories joined of the effective thanks to come through the goal. As mentioned, the present teaching strategies and approaches' main purpose is to involve learners into learning English actively. As a result, all the teaching is learner-centered rather than teacher-centered. This article would be very useful for not only English teachers at schools, but also teachers who work with mixed classes in other educational centers.

The importance of implementing cooperative learning strategies among multi-aged groups is becoming a big issue that must be solved, since new educational institutions are being established. For instance, professional schools, which provide learners with 5th degree, and educational centers are taking a significant role in our country. Both educational institutions do not have age limit for learners, however, teaching them in a proper way and using effective methods are in target now. Using traditional methods not always gives us better results, instead, addressing to modern methodology and adjusting it to the current situation seems to be the reasonable way to overcome emerging language gaps.

Past studies are primarily focused on the importance of grouping in cooperative learning and implementation the very method among seniors. Grouping, on the other hand, is considered to be one of the basic points. Research data indicates that students selected grouping is more preferred way, meaning that students are better to choose their partners or groups themselves. According to Wichadee and Orawiwatnakul (2012) the effect of cooperative language learning was not only improving learners' language skills, but also creates a supportive learning environment among students.

In history of the world, education was available only for those who could afford it. However, the need to educate massive illiterate population gained special attention of the government and the need to provide people with proper classrooms became another big issue. The multi-age grouping concept was introduced by Horace Mann in midcenturies became the solution of many problems. By 2000s, this new approach had been the target of researchers.

Employing a multiage technique to coaching college students builds on the belief that it may be individualized to fulfill the developmental desires of college students. Several research have seemed into the connection among multiage grouping and educational success. Inconsistent effects were discovered in studies reviews. Some researches declare that scholars in multiage school rooms do higher on standardized success assessments. Inconsistencies in studies consequences, in line with Veenman (1995), can be associated with an ambiguous idea of multiage schooling. Other researchers blame ambiguous studies consequences on a loss of element in records processing and inadequate controls for variations among experimental and manage circumstances, notwithstanding the reality that experimental research have to be designed to account for those discrepancies. In different cases, the compelled venture of each college students and instructors to multiage school rooms may despite, variations in research findings, studies that show significant achievement outcomes for pupils in multiage classrooms above single-age schools show linguistic advances. Both high- and low-ability pupils have benefited from the program. Long-term research has demonstrated that the benefits of multiage classrooms grow as students remain in multiage classes for extended periods of time. In the academic world, consistent reports across research of specific benefits of multiage grouping in the field of socio-emotional development back up the advantages. When compared to peers in typical graded classrooms, students in multiage classrooms have more positive views toward school, more leadership abilities, higher self-esteem, and increased pro-social and fewer aggressive behaviors. These characteristics have been found to have a positive impact on achievement outcomes in both traditional and multiage classes. The inconsistent effects in the academic arena are surprising, given the consistent favorable benefits of multiage grouping in the socio-emotional realm. The adoption of a developmentally appropriate strategy to teaching, such as teaming, cooperative group work, integrated curriculum, and encouragement of student interactions, is a consistent component in studies that indicate higher achievement outcomes for multiage students above same-age students. The use of developmentally appropriate teaching approaches in creating favorable achievement outcomes is supported by research. Furthermore, a large amount of evidence supports the use of cooperative educational efforts over competitive or individualistic educational efforts. Slavin's research, on the other hand, shows that peer interaction does not improve learning in and of itself. Learning

enhancement, on the other hand, is dependent on how the teacher directs such encounters.

When figuring out if cooperative learning is a technique suitable on your lesson, it's critical to recognize the diverse kinds. There are 3 typically identified styles of cooperative learning: informal learning groups, formal learning groups and cooperative base groups. Each type has its own cause and application.

Informal Learning Groups. These are informal short-term meetings with little structure. They usually consist of exercises in which students look to their neighbors for a few minutes to discuss topics and concepts. Informal groups are usually small and consist of 2-3 people. For rapid activities such as comprehension testing, brainstorming, rapid problem solving, summarization, and reviews, it is best to use informal research groups. These groups are a great way to divide a lecture by allowing students to discuss concepts with colleagues for a few minutes. It can be summarized as a teaching material on the go. Informal groups are especially useful for breaking the story into smaller chunks with group activities in between. This strategy reduces lecture time, but increases the amount of material held by students and the convenience of interaction.

Formal Learning Groups. Formal studying corporations are given an undertaking or challenge and should end it collectively. The maximum not unusual place utility of cooperative studying is on this form of group. Members of a set may go on long-time period tasks collectively for numerous weeks. These are the corporations wherein college students look at and exercise the various approaches for cooperating with one another. The instructor has hooked up a clean shape for those corporations, which incorporates undertaking and behavior standards. Depending at the undertaking, formal studying corporations is probably heterogeneous or homogeneous. Most corporations of 3 to 4 human beings' paintings well; any greater than 5 individuals can turn out to be unproductive. Formal studying corporations may be used within side the study room to finish a challenge, remedy a chain of tasks, revise for a test, or write a report.

Cooperative base group. These groups differ from the previous two groups in that the basic co-operative group is a long-term, stable group that lasts for at least a year and is made up of people with different skills and perspectives. increase. The basic group should last at least one semester, but can last up to several years. Because these are long-term efforts, these groups tend to be more than just academic problem-solving groups. Community members often become

mutual personal support systems, building relationships and trust during the collaborative learning process. The purpose of a collaborative grassroots group is for members to fulfill their responsibilities among their peers and support each other by learning together. They provide a situation where students can support each other in science and other aspects of life. Group members make sure that everyone is doing their job and are responsible for contributing to each other. By implementing collaborative basic groups in such a way that students meet regularly during learning to solve collaborative learning tasks, students develop in a scientifically developed, cognitively and socially sound way. We can provide the permanent support and supervision you need to do.

It is permissible to use multiple types of groups at the same time. For example, you can assign a formal research group to a project, but use an informal group during a lesson where the formal group is not linked. If there are classes that are difficult to collaborate with, students may need many opportunities to practice the collaboration. Start and move towards a more formal co-learning situation.

According to Slavin (1983) strategies of cooperative studying traditionally include number one additives: a cooperative incentive shape (Arend's definition) and a cooperative undertaking shape. Cooperative incentive shape is what maximum theorists imply after they consult with cooperation. Slavin persevered that the important function of a cooperative incentive shape is that or extra people are interdependence for a praise they may proportion if they're successful. He illustrated, for example, if 3 human beings journeying in a vehicle assist push the auto out of the mud, they all gain from every other's efforts (via way of means of being capable of maintain the trip). All may be rewarded or none of them may be, relying on whether or not they prevail or now no longer. While cooperative undertaking systems are conditions wherein or extra people are allowed, encouraged, or required to paintings collectively on a few tasks, coordinating their efforts to finish the undertaking. Students' paintings cooperative tasks, however the undertaking themselves are wonderful every other. In one undertaking, for instance, one pupil might also additionally work to gather and pick dialogue materials, each other lead dialogue, the rests are likely a notary, front-instructor presenter, and so on. Slavin explained: For example, participants to an edited quantity are beneath a cooperative incentive shape (all of them gain if the book does nicely even though they by no means meet or communicate with each other (i.e., they're now no longer beneath a cooperative undertaking shape)⁵. As to remind, intention shape is the quantity of interdependences (individualistic, competitive, and cooperative) required to

college students whilst operating collectively. Those 3 additives undergo a few strategies which accommodate coaching studying procedure primarily based totally on instructors and college students need. Three maximum famous and normally used strategies till now are Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD), Jigsaw, and Group Investigation (GI). As to know, a technique is the important cognizance of an approach. The originators of a technique have arrived at selections approximately varieties of activities, roles of instructors and learners, the forms of cloth to be able to be helpful, and a few versions of syllabus organization. Methods encompass diverse approaches and strategies

Currently, co-operative education up to foreign language instruction is being conducted in the classroom. Collaborative proficiency and English as a second or foreign language in the classroom is a great integration (Kagan, 2001). There is research development focused primarily on the impact and effectiveness of collaborative mastering in classroom foreign language training. According to Crandall (1999), collaborative language skills have the wonderful elements of learning a language, motivating, relieving tension, stimulating motivation, selling self-esteem, and supporting outstanding proficiency.

The collaborative learning method promotes active learning of students through the development of a realistic language environment. By conducting collaborative learning within the framework of foreign language coaching, students are provided with additional opportunities for participation, experience, interaction and cooperation in foreign language learning. At cooperating institutions, college students have the same goal of drawing together, interacting face-to-face, mastering and supporting each other (Borich, 2007). Collaborative learning is probably the ideal way to achieve this goal, as language teachers need to create a vibrant mastering ecosystem where college children study on their own with many blessings. Suwantarathip and Wichadee (2010) tested the effectiveness of co-learning to relieve tensions in learning a foreign language and examined its impact on language proficiency assessment of 40 college students. It was found that the tensions of college students in learning foreign languages were dramatically alleviated after they learned the joint learning technique. In addition, there was a growing desire for joint learning among all university students. In a collaborative language proficiency environment, institutional coaching has become a learner-centric approach, and organizations have been designed so that each member does their job to achieve their goals. They argued that previous studies have shown that the effects of collaborative language acquisition are no longer the best language skills for

advanced learners, but they also create a supportive environment for proficiency. Their research recommends that, despite the great effects of collaborative teaching techniques, it is necessary to acquire some knowledge for teaching control modes in order to avoid problems that actually occur in the end. This method enhances basic social skills, improves communication skills, presents a great version for lifelong learning, and brings additional doctrinal enrichment to all members of the institution. It is believed to promote a great environment for mastering.⁴ Constructivist approaches, including collaborative teaching enable the enhancement of cognitive and meta-cognitive skills needed to build real-world knowledge. Nevertheless, collaborative mastering is a powerful approach to dealing with multiple intelligences.

Some benefits of collaborative teaching in the context of foreign language school spaces have been recognized as a result of the changing perception of communicative language coaching. By easing student tensions, encouraging positive attitudes toward language skills, and boosting self-esteem, Crandall (1999) also adds to the efficacy of collaborative language skills. It is also anticipated that a flexible learning environment created by collaboration rather than conflict will give college students more autonomy.

Given the drawbacks of cooperative learning, not all college students are able to engage in co-learning in the same way or with the highest level of diligence. Furthermore, Pica (1994) observed that students in foreign language programs tend to use their native tongue if teachers are not involved. According to Richards and Rodgers (2001), instructors who may find it difficult to adjust to shifts in their roles within the classroom are further burdened by the cooperative command of the space.

The literature reviews mentioned above examined teaching studies and concentrated on the key components—high interdependence, personality obligations, and institutional processing—that are necessary for their successful implementation.

We can conclude by noting that nearly all students stated that they learn about individual differences through communication. They understand that there are multiple approaches to solving an issue. Since most of them share the same viewpoint, this led to them developing mutual trust within the group. They realize that moving together would benefit them all as a result of this. In order to arrive at a solution, they work in groups, exchange ideas, identify problems, and ultimately hone higher order thinking abilities. The majority believe that while working together to complete a task, they learn how to cooperate by being

respectful of one another's opinions. They indicate that this is also a way of learning to be tolerant. By this way, they grow the feeling of respect towards both themselves and the others.

Students know that when the group has a common task to achieve, the reward is also common. Because of this, the members encourage each other to reach the goal and this naturally motivates the group members. As another result of motivation, it can be said that students grow positive attitude towards school, learning and the class. It is obvious that most students prefer studying in cooperative learning environments rather than working individually in case doing the distribution of task carefully, arranging the groups sensibly to avoid giving harm to creativity, sociability and motivation of the students.

The classroom often offers a student's first experiences practicing most life skills. Teachers should deliberately create opportunities for students to cooperate with each other, share responsibilities, solve problems, and control conflict. These opportunities can be found in cooperative learning, which differs from individualistic or traditional learning where students work independently, sometimes even against each other. Cooperative learning activities require students to work together in small groups to complete a project or activity, operating as a team to help each other succeed. Cooperative learning, of course, teaches a number of social and emotional skills, but it also gives students the opportunity to learn from each other. Studies show that peer learning in which students explain concepts and ideas to each other has the potential to improve comprehension considerably.

In conclusion, cooperative learning produces critical experiences that other learning structures cannot. The following skills that are developed through regular and effective cooperative learning are just a few of many. Students who work together as a team share a common goal: a successful project. This can only be achieved through the combined efforts of the whole group. The ability to work as a team towards a common goal is an invaluable quality to have in the real world, especially for careers.

Cooperative education within mixed-age groups stands as a powerful catalyst for holistic development. By promoting collaborative learning, social-emotional growth, and preparing individuals for the complexities of a diverse society, this approach holds immense value in shaping the educational landscape. As we navigate the ever-evolving realm of education, recognizing the benefits of cooperative education in mixed-age groups becomes paramount for fostering inclusive, empathetic, and well-rounded individuals.

It takes time, patience, and tenacity to enable collaborative learning. The more you learn about cooperative learning and practice your skills, the better you will get results and the more benefits. All collaborative learning activities help students practice working in teams. "Teams should be able to act with the same determination and concentration as motivated individuals," said Bill Gates, co-founder of Microsoft. The Team Building Exercise teaches students to trust each other to achieve together more than is possible in other ways.

References:

1. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press.
2. Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R. T., & Smith, K. A. (1998). *Active Learning: Cooperation in the College Classroom*. Edina, MN: Interaction Book Company.
3. Slavin, R. E. (1990). *Cooperative Learning: Theory, Research, and Practice*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
4. Cohen, E. G. (1994). Restructuring the Classroom: Conditions for Productive Small Groups. *Review of Educational Research*, 64(1), 1-35.
5. Topping, K. J. (1996). The Effectiveness of Peer Tutoring in Further and Higher Education: A Typology and Review of the Literature. *Higher Education*, 32(3), 321-345.
6. Wang, M. C., Haertel, G. D., & Walberg, H. J. (1993). Toward a Knowledge Base for School Learning. *Review of Educational Research*, 63(3), 249-294.
7. Brophy, J. E. (1989). Research on the Self-Fulfilling Prophecy and Teacher Expectations. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 81(3), 371-386.
8. Lou, Y., Abrami, P. C., Spence, J. C., Poulsen, C., Chambers, B., & d'Apollonia, S. (1996). Within-Class Grouping: A Meta-Analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 66(4), 423-458.
9. Gillies, R. M., & Boyle, M. (2010). Teachers' Reflections on Cooperative Learning: Issues of Implementation. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(4), 933-940.
10. Rubin, K. H., Bukowski, W., & Parker, J. G. (2006). Peer Interactions, Relationships, and Groups. In N. Eisenberg (Ed.), *Handbook of Child Psychology: Social, Emotional, and Personality Development* (6th ed., Vol. 3, pp. 571-645). John Wiley & Sons.
11. Cuseo, J. (2007). The Empirical Case Against Large Class Size: Adverse Effects on the Teaching, Learning, and Retention of First-Year Students. *Journal of Faculty Development*, 21(1), 5-21.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

12. Brooks, J. G., & Brooks, M. G. (1999). In Search of Understanding: The Case for Constructivist Classrooms. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
13. Kagan, S. (1994). Cooperative Learning. San Clemente, CA: Kagan Cooperative Learning.
14. Allport, G. W. (1954). The Nature of Prejudice. Addison-Wesley.
15. Brouwer, N., Korthagen, F., & Nieveen, N. (2005). Collaborative Action Research and the Development of Teachers' Professional Knowledge. Educational Action Research, 13(3), 307-326.